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**Multi spiral Computed Tomography Analysis of Chronic Lung Disease
Complications in Patients Who Have Undergone Covid-19 Pneumonia**

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During the pandemic of a new coronavirus infection, the question of the possible consequences of the infection, the assessment of post-inflammatory changes and quality of life is widely discussed in clinical practice. As of November 14, 2021, according to the World Health Organization website, 254 million cases of the new coronavirus infection COVID-19 were registered, of which 5.1 million were fatal, 229.1 million patients recovered. Among the complications of infection caused by SARS-CoV-2, complications associated with damage to the lungs, heart and blood vessels, kidneys and central nervous system are distinguished [1, 2]. Among domestic and foreign publications, there are isolated works devoted to the long-term results of COVID-19 treatment [3].

The purpose of the study. To evaluate the features of the course of the inflammatory process, to study the condition of the lung tissue according to the results of multisection computed tomography (MSCT) 1, 3 and 6

months after completion of treatment in patients with COVID-19-associated pneumonia.

Material and methods. The Main Military Clinical Hospital of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation analyzed the results of examination and treatment of 60 patients (41 (68%) men and 19 (32%) women) aged 37 to 81 years (average age – 52.5 ± 5.1 years) who were treated in the period from March 2020 to March 2021 about viral pneumonia caused by COVID-

19. The data obtained using classical radiography, MSCT of patients with varying degrees of severity of lung tissue damage, at admission, after 1, 3 and 6 months were analyzed. Depending on the degree of lung tissue damage, the patients were divided into four groups of 15 people each: with minimal damage according to computed tomography (CT-1), with mild damage (CT-2), moderate (CT- 3) and severe damage (CT-4). The criteria for inclusion in the study were the presence of clinical signs of COVID-19 viral pneumonia, the identification of changes in the lungs

characteristic of this disease using radiation diagnostics methods and positive results of reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction on SARSCoV-2. The exclusion criteria were the presence of bacterial pneumonia and other acute diseases of the

upper respiratory tract. The main method of assessing the state of the pulmonary parenchyma after a new coronavirus infection was multi-slice computed tomography (MSCT) performed on a 16-slice computed tomograph Toshiba Aquilion (Japan); 128-slice computed tomograph Philips (Netherlands); 64-slice computed tomograph Siemens Go Top (Germany).

The severity of pneumonia was assessed on the basis of criteria approved by the order of the Moscow Department of Health of 08.04.2020 No. 373 and the order of 16.04.2020 No. 10-18-231/20. The degree of damage to the lung tissue was assessed by the volume of involvement of its parenchyma: does not correspond to pneumonia – CT-0, minimal – CT- 1 (less than 25%), mild – CT-2 (25-50%), moderate – CT-3 (50-75%) or severe – CT-4 (75- 100%) [1]. Laboratory diagnostics of COVID-19 was carried out by reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction. The material from the patient's oropharynx was examined. The study was conducted in the laboratories of Rospotrebnadzor and the Main Center for State Sanitary and Epidemiological Surveillance of the National Guard Troops of the Russian Federation. Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out using the Microsoft Office 2016 software package.

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Homiladorlarda yod tanqisligi va uning oldini olish profilaktikasi

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Annotatsiya: Homila rivojlanishining turli bosqichlarida qalqonsimon bez gormonlari turli funksiyalarni bajaradi. Homiladorlik davrida ular turli organlarning, shu jumladan miyaning o'sishini va rivojlanishini nazorat qiladi. Shunday qilib, ular homiladorlik davrida to'g'ri o'sish, shuningdek, homilaning jismoniy va aqliy rivojlanishi uchun juda muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: Homiladorlik, yod, tanqislik, profilaktika, chora – tadbirlar, oldini olish, davolash.

Аннотация: Гормоны щитовидной железы выполняют разные функции на разных этапах развития плода. Во время беременности они контролируют рост и развитие различных органов, включая мозг. Таким образом, они очень важны для правильного роста во время беременности, а также физического и умственного развития плода.

Ключевые слова: Беременность, йод, дефицит, профилактика, меры, профилактика, лечение.

Abstract: Thyroid hormones perform different functions at different stages of fetal development. During pregnancy, they control the growth and development of various organs, including the brain. Thus, they are very important for proper growth during pregnancy, as well as the physical and mental development of the fetus.

Key words: Pregnancy, iodine, deficiency, prevention, measures, prevention, treatment.

Homiladorlik davrida ayol odatdagidan ko'ra ko'proq yod iste'mol qilishi kerak. Ushbu mineral moddaga bo'lgan ehtiyojning oshishi bir necha sabablarga bog'liq. Birinchidan, yo'ldosh-bu o'ziga xos fermentning boy manbai hisoblanadi (gormon molekulasining ichki halqasini deyodizatsiyalovchi 3-turdagi deyodinaza), u qalqonsimon bez gormoni bo'lgan tiroksinni faolsizlantirib, uni biologik faol bo'lmagan shaklga o'tkazadi. Shuning uchun organizmning tireoid gormonlarga bo'lgan ehtiyoji ortadi, bu esa iste'mol qilinadigan yod miqdorini oshirishni talab qiladi. Bundan tashqari, homiladorlikning dastlabki bosqichlarida inson xorionik gonadotropinining (IXG) yuqori konsentratsiyasi qalqonsimon bezdagi tireoid gormonlarning sintezini stimullaydi. Ushbu "qo'shimcha" tireoid gormonlari qon va platsenta orqali homila organizmiga o'tadi, chunki embrion qalqonsimon bezi faqat homiladorlikning 20-haftasidan keyin o'z tireoid gormonlarini ishlab chiqaradi.

Homiladorlikning ikkinchi yarmida homilaning tireoid gormonlariga bo'lgan ehtiyoj oshadi va yod platsenta orqali oson o'tishi sababli, onaning yodga ehtiyoji ham oshadi.

Bundan tashqari, homilador ayollarda yodga bo'lgan ehtiyoj quyidagi o'zgarishlar bilan bog'liq:

- Yodning buyrak klirensi oshadi.
- Yod va tireoid gormonlarning taqsimlanish hajmi oshadi.
- Qalqonsimon bez gormonlarining ko‘p miqdori qon oqsillari bilan bog‘lanadi.

Modda almashinuvining bunday o‘zgarishlariga javoban homilador ayollarda tireoid gormonlar ishlab chiqarilishi (erta davrdan boshlab) homilador bo‘lmagan ayollarga nisbatan deyarli 50% ga oshadi. Ishlab chiqarishni ko‘paytirish oziq-ovqat bilan yoki qo‘shimchalar shaklida tegishli miqdorda yod tushishini talab qiladi. Shu munosabat bilan YUNISEF, ICCIDD va JSST kunlik yod iste‘molini 250 mkg ga (homilador bo‘lmagan ayollar uchun 150 mkg bilan solishtirganda) oshirishni tavsiya qiladilar. Turli tashkilotlar homilador ayollar uchun yod iste‘mol qilishning turli me‘yorlarini tavsiya qiladilar (150 dan 290 mkg/kuniga) .

O‘ziq moddalar va energiyaga bo‘lgan ehtiyojlarning fiziologik me‘yorlariga ko‘ra, O‘zbekistonda homilador ayollarga kuniga 220 mkg yod tavsiya etiladi. Yodga bo‘lgan kundalik ehtiyojni ta‘minlashning mumkin bo‘lgan usullaridan biri oziq-ovqat tarkibida yetarli miqdorda yod iste‘mol qilishdir. Yod ta‘minoti me‘yorda bo‘lgan hududlarda 200 mkg yodni quyidagi yangi mahsulotlarni iste‘mol qilish orqali olish mumkin:

- 240 g dengiz balig‘i
- 4 kg go‘sht
- 4 l sut
- 2 kg tuxum
- 7 kg sabzavot

Shuning uchun, homiladorlik davrida yod miqdorini ta‘minlash uchun tarkibida yod bo‘lgan qo‘shimchalarni qabul qilishni hisobga olish kerak.

Homilador ayollarda yod holati

Yevropa mintaqasi mamlakatlarida homiladorlik davrida yod tanqisligi rivojlanishi tez-tezligini baholash uchun (JSST), 2000- 2015 yillar oralig'ida homilador ayollardan olingan so'nggi so'rov natijalari tahlil qilindi. Ayrim davlatlarda milliy tadqiqotlar ma'lumotlari mavjud emas edi, shuning uchun tadqiqotchilar kamida 100 ayol ishtirok etgan submilliy tadqiqotlarning umumlashtirilgan ma'lumotlarini tahlil qildilar. Umuman olganda, bu usul Yevropada o'sha davrda yashagan homilador ayollarning 58% to'g'risida ma'lumotlarini olish imkonini berdi. Natijalar: faqat 10 mamlakatda homiladorlik davrida yod iste'moli yetarli edi, 21 mamlakatda homilador ayollar juda kam yod iste'mol qilgan ekanlar. Bu shuni anglatadiki, Yevropada homiladorlik davrida ayollarning 2/3 qismi kam miqdorda yod iste'mol qiladi.

Homiladorlik davrida yod tanqisligi oqibatlari

Shubhasiz, homilador ayollarda yod tanqisligi kattalardagi singari bir xil oqibatlariga va kasalliklarga olib kelishi mumkin. Biroq, (va bu juda ham muhim), u homila uchun ayniqsa jiddiy oqibatlariga olib kelishi mumkin.

Og'ir darajadagi yod tanqisligining oqibatlari:

- O'lik tug'ilish xavfining ortishi
- Homila asab tizimi rivojlanishining buzilishi
- Aqliy zaiflik va nevrologik kasalliklar rivojlanishi bilan kechuvchi bosh miyaning ortga qaytmas zararlanishi
- Bunday ortga qaytmas kasalliklarning eng jiddiy shakli kretinizm deb ataladi, u aqliy zaiflik, karsoqovlik, spastik diplegiya (bolalar bosh miya falajining shakli), g'ilaylik va pakanalikka olib keladi.

Biroq, homilaga salbiy taʼsir faqat ogʻir darajadagi yod tanqisligi bilan bogʻliq emas. Homiladorlik davrida yengil va oʻrta darajadagi yod tanqisligi bolaning kognitiv funksiyasiga taʼsir qilishi mumkin. Bu, soʻzsiz, homiladorlik davrida yod isteʼmoliga eʼtibor berish qanchalik muhimligini koʻrsatadi; bundan tashqari, qoʻshimcha yod qabuli (masalan, Yodomarin® 100 va 200 preparatlari koʻrinishida) homilador ayollarda yod tanqisligi kasalliklarini rivojlanish xavfini kamaytirishning oddiy usuli hisoblanadi.

Biroq, homiladorlik davrida, bu mikroelementga boʻlgan ehtiyoj ortganida, yetarli miqdorda yod olish uchun bu maslahatlarga rioya qilishning oʻzi yetarli boʻlmazligi mumkin. Bu ayniqsa, yod holati pastligi tufayli yod tanqisligi xavfi juda yuqori boʻlgan va oʻsimliklar va hayvonot mahsulotlari juda kam miqdorda yod saqlovchi hududlarda yashovchi ayollarga tegishlidir.

Bunday holda yodning kerakli miqdorini yetarli darajada isteʼmol qilish va yod tanqisligini profilaktikasini taʼminlashning oddiy va samarali usuli – bu tarkibida yod saqlaydigan qoʻshimchalarni qabul qilish boʻlishi mumkin. Mumkin boʻlgan variantlardan biri tarkibida yod saqlovchi preparatlarni har kuni qabul qilishdir (masalan, Yodomarin® preparati). Agar yod tanqisligini oldini olish uchun normal ovqatlanishda kerakli yod miqdorini kafolatlash mumkin boʻlmasa, yodni quyida belgilangan qiymatlardan kam boʻlmagan miqdorda qabul qilish kerak:

Yodomarin® preparatini tibbiyotda qoʻllanilishiga doir yoʻriqnomaga muvofiq tavsiya etilgan yod qabuli

Homilador ayollar: 200 mkg yod yoki Yodomarin® 200 preparatini 1 tabletkasi kuniga bir marta

Ushbu tavsiya etilgan dozalar kunlik yod talabini qoplashi va yod tanqisligi va uning oqibatlarini profilaktikasining oddiy va qulay usuli bo‘lib xizmat qilishi mumkin.

Amerika tireoid assotsiatsiyasi (American thyroid Association), masalan, shimoliy Amerikada yashovchi barcha homilador va emizikli ayollar uchun kuniga 150 mkg yod iste‘mol qilishni tavsiya qiladi. Yaqinda Endokrinologik jamiyati (Endocrine Society), teratologlar jamiyati (Teratology Society) va Amerika pediatriya akademiyasi (American Academy of Pediatrics) tarkibida yod bolgan qo‘shimchalardan foydalanishni qo‘llab-quvvatladi.

O‘ziq moddalar va energiyaga bo‘lgan ehtiyojning fiziologik me‘yorlariga ko‘ra, O‘zbekistonda homilador va emizikli ayollarga kuniga 220 mkg yod tavsiya etiladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

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The Problem of Loanwords in Financial Terminology

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Keywords: Loanwords, financial terminology, Uzbek, English, ambiguity, standardization, financial innovation.

Abstract:

The globalized world fosters linguistic cross-pollination, with loanwords permeating the financial vocabulary of many languages. This essay explores the challenges and implications of using loanwords in financial terminology, focusing on Uzbek and English. While enriched lexicons are evident, issues of ambiguity, standardization, and adaptation to financial innovation arise. Analyzing historical influences and examining specific examples, this article advocates for cautious adoption of loanwords and prioritizes clear communication in the ever-evolving realm of finance.

Language mirrors societal dynamics, and in a globalized world, linguistic intermingling creates a fascinating phenomenon - loanwords. They enrich financial vocabularies but also pose challenges concerning understanding and standardization. This essay delves into the use of loanwords in Uzbek and English financial terminology, highlighting both benefits and drawbacks.

The infiltration of loanwords is a natural process arising from trade, cultural exchange, and geopolitical influences. Uzbek, a Turkic language, has integrated Persian, Arabic, and Russian terms, enriching its financial lexicon. However, this intermingling raises concerns about standardization, with "kredit" (loan) coexisting

with the native "qarz". English, a global lingua franca, too, contains numerous loanwords in finance, including "bank" (Italian) and "portfolio" (Dutch). Though integrated, these terms may hold nuances unseen by non-native speakers.

Loanwords in financial terminology present several challenges. Firstly, ambiguity and misinterpretation can arise due to nuanced meanings in the source language. Secondly, coexisting loanwords and native terms create a confusing duality, hindering standardization efforts. Finally, the rapid evolution of financial markets may outpace linguistic adaptation, leading to awkward loanword introductions or the creation of unclear new terms.

While loanwords enrich languages, their adoption in financial terminology necessitates caution. Precise communication within and across borders is paramount. Therefore, clear definitions, contextualization, and prioritization of readily understood language should guide the inclusion of loanwords. Additionally, considering historical linguistic influences and local terminology can foster smoother integration and understanding.

Loanwords in financial terminology highlight the interconnectedness of languages and the dynamic nature of linguistic evolution. While Uzbek and English have benefitted from loanwords, navigating their usage requires consideration of potential ambiguities, advocating for clarity and standardization in the ever-changing world of finance. By promoting clear communication and acknowledging the evolving financial landscape, we can master the maze of money, ensuring financial literacy and understanding across linguistic boundaries.

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THE ROLE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN STATE REGULATION

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ABSTRACT: The article discusses the importance of the digital economy, which is a modern requirement, and the benefits of its implementation in our country.

KEYWORDS: digital technology, digital economy, engineering, economics.

The increase in the share of innovative activity has led to the fact that innovations are the same such as minerals, production capacity and intellectual capacity the country's wealth began to be counted. Our country and each of its citizens effective use of innovative and scientific and technical potential in the interests of formation of a multi-sectoral innovation policy in our country and its implementation to

increase - there is no possibility without creating legal bases. The head of our state said, "... our country is an international informatio 8 in 2019 according to the index of development of communication technologies although it has risen to the top, it is still far behind. Most ministries and agencies, It is also true that companies are far from digital technologies. Of course, Building a digital economy requires infrastructure, a lot of money and labor we know very well that it requires resources. However, no matter how difficult it is If we don't start work today, when will we start?! Tomorrow will be too late. To this end, active transition to the digital economy is one of our most important tasks in the next 5 year will be. The role of the digital economy in the economy in determining the competitiveness of countries in the process of globalization is unique. No matter which industry or sector of the economy we look at, we see the place of digital technologies in all of them. From services in the country's banking system, we can see the share of innovative digital technologies at the level of public services. The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is a modern stage of development, which is characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. Digital technologies not only improve the quality of products and services, but also reduces costs. At the same time, I am very worried and they are also effective in eliminating the most serious evil that bothers us - corruption is a tool. We all need to understand this deeply. State and community management, widely introducing digital technologies in the social sphere and increasing productivity, one in other words, people's lives can be dramatically improved." President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his appeals to the Oliy Majlis 202 declared the year as the "Year of Development of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy" Modernizing Uzbekistan today aims not only to develop, but to become one of the strongest countries as a result of comprehensive reforms implemented in various

spheres of society. In the digital economy, information in digital form is the main element of production in all socio-economic areas, and the gradual transition to such an economic system will further increase the competitiveness of our country on a global scale, the quality of life of citizens, create new jobs, and enable rapid economic growth. creates and ensures national independence. In order to further develop the digital economy in our country, in order to ensure the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 No. With the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 409 of June 25, 2020 "On measures to organize the activities of certain organizations within the system of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" at the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communications Development The state institution "Digital Economy Research Center" was established. The main functions of the center are as follows:

- on the basis of comprehensive analytical and practical studies, to assess the impact of digitization processes on production and economic sectors, and to develop proposals for expanding the digital transformation of the country's economy in the future;
- to study and analyze the problems that arise in the wide implementation of the digital economy in the activities of state bodies and economic sectors, and to prepare comprehensively based proposals for their solutions;
- to study the experience of leading countries on the level of development of the digital economy and electronic government and to prepare proposals for their application to state bodies, organizations and economic sectors;

- formation of conceptual and methodological bases for the introduction of "smart" and other promising technologies, as well as large-scale data processing technologies in various sectors of the economy;
- development of long-term prospects for the development of electronic government and digital economy, based on the implementation of scientific and technical and research activities in the priority directions of the introduction of digital technologies.

In general, the Digital economy is a set of economic activities closely related to electronic business and electronic commerce based on digital technologies, as well as digital goods and services produced and sold as a result of this activity. The fact that the positions of deputy heads in the field of digitization have been introduced in the existing ministries and agencies in our country is also a factor in the development of the digital economy. According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 28, 2020 "On measures for the widespread introduction of the digital economy and electronic government" by 2023, the share of the digital economy in the country's gross domestic product and services in this field it is envisaged to increase the volume by 3 times, and to increase their export to 100 million dollars. Representatives of all spheres understand well that the widespread introduction of digital technologies can serve the development of the state and society, as well as the development of the social sphere, and can dramatically improve people's lives. Instead of conclusions and suggestions, it is worth saying that humanity is for development. It is clear only if it is carried out with the aim of making life easier the plan can be used. In the current period and near future of human development in terms of the quality of economic sectors, social sphere and state management system development is directly related to the widespread introduction of digital technologies is going. The prospect of our country's

development is the development of the digital economy and relies on the level of coverage of digital technologies. To achieve this the following basic conditions and priorities for the development of the digital economy it is appropriate to list the directions. It is no exaggeration to say that the literacy of the population is a step forward in this regard. It is the same in our country digital technology for public literacy at leisure. At the same time, the process of training specialists in this field is being strengthened. Leading specialists are currently lacking in digitization is also hindering; Number of activities of total schools in the field of secondary education. If we are not connected to technology, it is difficult to see the future towards a long digital life and hard work; an enterprise that is currently operating increasing the level of knowledge of employees, suitable for modern technical activities incentives that create a favorable opportunity for special tests or monthly salary. If we don't use it, we will separate the techniques in this field from the breath of the past we can't; Although the above suggestions may seem simple to you, they are actually ours that you and we can be the prelude to our foundation for future development we know well.

Some may wonder why the digital economy is needed and what it will provide. Digital economy does not mean only Blockchain technology and its use in international financial markets or cryptocurrencies. Of course, Blockchain technology and cryptocurrencies are also part of the digital economy. But the term "Digital Economy" refers to the economy conducted with the help of digital communications and IT. It can also be seen as a means of ending the underground economy. Because, firstly, all transactions must be registered electronically, and secondly, will be transparent. In addition, due to the use of new IT technologies in production, the cost of products and services will decrease.

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Hozirgi zamon psixologiyasi va uning boshqa fanlar tizimida tutgan o‘rni

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada hozirgi zamon psixologiyasi va uning boshqa fanlar tizimida tutgan o‘rni haqida yoritib berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Psixologiya, falsafa, ong, tafakkur, sotsiologiya, kibernetika.

Abstract: This article describes modern psychology and its place in the system of other sciences.

Key words: Psychology, philosophy, consciousness, thinking, sociology, cybernetics.

Аннотация: В данной статье описывается современная психология и ее место в системе других наук.

Ключевые слова: Психология, философия, сознание, мышление, социология, кибернетика.

Psixologiya yaxlit va mustaqil fan sifatida odamlarda gumanistik mentalitetning shakllanishiga xizmat qilib, inson omiliga aloqadorligi uning shu yo‘nalishdagi muammolarni ma‘lum ma‘noda o‘rganadigan barcha fanlar bilan bevosita aloqasini taqozo etadi. Bular birinchi navbatda ijtimoiy-gumanitar fan sohalari bo‘lib, psixologiyaning ular orasidagi mavqei o‘ziga xos va yetakchidir.

1. Falsafa va uning oxirgi paytlarda shakllanib, rivojlanib borayotgan ijtimoiy falsafa qismi bilan bo‘lgan aloqa bu ikkala fanning inson va uning hayoti mohiyatini

to'la anglash va uning rivojlanish tendentsiyalarini belgilashdagi o'rni va ahamiyatidan kelib chiqadi. Tabiat, jamiyat va inson tafakkurining rivojlanishiga oid bo'lgan umumiy qonuniyatlar va printsiplarni psixologiya falsafaning bazasidan oladi va shu bilan birga o'zi ham inson ongi va tafakkuri qonuniyatlari sohasidagi yutuqlari bilan falsafani boy ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishiga yordam beradi. Shuni alohida ta'kidlash joizki, mustaqillik mafkurasi va milliy ongning shakllanishiga taalluqli umumiy ilmiy qonuniyatlarni izlashda ham yurtimiz sharoitida bu ikkala fan-falsafa va psixologiyaning hamkorligi bevosita sezilmoqda. Bu bog'liqlik avvalo yangicha tafakkur va dunyoqarashni shakllantirish muammosi kundalang turgan tarixiy davrda milliy mafkura va milliy g'oyani shakllantirish kabi dolzarb vazifani bajarishga xizmat qilmoqda.

2. Sotsiologiya fani ham yangicha ijtimoiy munosabatlar sharoitida o'z taraqqiyotining muhim bosqichiga o'tgan ekan, psixologiya ushbu fan erishgan yutuqlardan ham foydalanadi, ham ularning ko'lami kengayishiga baholi qudrat xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, psixologiyadan mustaqil ravishda ajralib chiqqan, bugungi taraqqiyot davrimizda alohida ahamiyat kasb etgan ijtimoiy psixologiyaning sotsiologiya bilan aloqasi uzviy bo'lib, ular jamiyatda ijtimoiy taraqqiyot va progressni ta'minlash ishiga xizmat qiladi. Qolaversa, xuquqiy, demokratik davlat qurish ishini sobitqadamlik bilan amalga oshirayotgan O'zbekiston aholisining xuquqiy madaniyatini va demokratik o'zgarishlarga psixologik jihatdan tayyorligini amalda ta'minlash, bu sohada muntazam tarzda ijtimoiy fikr va insonlar dunyoqarashlaridagi o'zgarishlarni o'z vaqtida o'rganish, bashorat qilish va taraqqiyot mezonlarini ishlab chiqishda ikkala fanlar metodologiyasi va metodlarini birlashtirish tadbqiqiy ahamiyat kasb etadi.

3. Pedagogika bilan psixologiyaning o'zaro hamkorligi va aloqasi an'anaviy va azaliy bo'lib, ularning yosh avlod tarbiyasini zamon talablari ruhida amalga

oshirishdagi roli va nufuzi o'ziga xosdir. Respublikamizda amalga oshirilayotgan yangi «Ta'lim to'g'risidagi Qonun» hamda «Kadrlar tayyorlashning milliy Dasturi»ni amalga oshirish ham ikki fan hamkorligi va o'zaro aloqasini har qachongidan ham dolzarb qilib qo'ydi. Milliy dasturda e'tirof etilgan yangicha modeldagi shaxsni kamol toptirish, uning chuqur bilimlar sohibi bo'lib etishishi, barkamolligini kafolatlovchi shart-sharoitlar orasida yangi pedagogik texnologiyalarini ta'lim va tarbiya jarayonlariga tadbiiq etishda pedagogikaning o'z uslub va qoidalari yetarli bo'lmaydi.

Shuning uchun ham psixologiya u bilan hamkorlikda yosh avlod ongining ta'lim olish davrlaridagi rivojlanish tendentsiyalaridan tortib, toki yangicha o'qitish texnologiyalarini bola tomonidan o'zlashtirilishi va undagi aqliy hamda intellektual qobiliyatlarga nechog'lik ta'sir ko'rsatayotganligini o'rganish asosida ta'lim-tarbiya ishini tashkil etish psixologiyadagi metodlarni didaktik metodlar bilan uyg'unlashtirishni taqozo etadi. Ayniqsa, ma'naviy barkamollik tamoyillarini maktabda va yangi tipdagi ta'lim muassasalarida joriy etish ham shaxs psixologiyasini teran bilgan holda o'qitishning eng ilg'or va zamonaviy shakllarini amaliyotga tadbiiq etishni nazarda tutadi.

4. Tabiiy fanlar: biologiya, fiziologiya, ximiya, fizika va b.q. Psixik xodisalar va jarayonlarning tabiiy fiziologik mexanizmlarini tushunish va shu orqali ularning kechishi qonuniyatlarini ob'ektiv o'rganish uchun material beradi. Ayniqsa, bosh miyaning hamda markaziy asab sistemasining psixik faoliyatlarini boshqarishda va ularni muvofiqlashtirishdagi rolini e'tirof etgan holda psixologiya fani tabiiy fanlar erishgan yutuqlar va ulardagi tadqiqot uslublaridan omilkorona foydalanadi.

Masalan, shaxs qobiliyatlarini diagnostika qilish uning tug'ma layoqatlari hamda orttirilgan sifatlarini bir vaqtda bilishni taqozo etgani sababli, o'sha tabiiy layoqatning xususiyatlarini aniqlashda psixofiziologiyaning qator usullaridan (miya

assimetriyasi qonunlari, miya bioritmlarini yozib olish, neyrodinamik xodisalarni aniqlash, qon aylanish va tana haroratini o'lchash metodlari) o'z o'rnida foydalanadi va biologiya, anatomiya, fiziologiya, neyrofiziologiya kabi fanlarning shu kungacha erishgan yutuqlaridan foydalanadi. Shuning uchun tabiiy fanlar sohasida erishilgan barcha

yutuqlar psixologiyaning predmetini mukammalroq yoritishga o'z hissasini qo'shgan.

5. Kibernetika fani sohasidagi yorishilgan yutuqlar psixologiya uchun ham ahamiyatli va zarur bo'lib, u inson shaxsining o'z-o'zini boshqarish va psixik jarayonlarni takomillashtirish borasida axborotlar texnologiyasi va kibernetika tomonidan qo'lga kiritilgan yutuqlar va tadqiqot metodlari, maxsus dasturdan o'z o'rnida foydalanadi.

Ayniqsa, ma'lumotlar asri bo'lgan XX va har bir alohida ma'lumotning qadr-qimmatini oshirish kutilayotgan XXI asrda informatsion texnologiyalar va modellashtirish borasida psixologiya hamda kibernetika hamkorligining salohiyati yanada ortadi.

Masalan, oddiy muloqot jarayonini yanada takomillashtirish, har bir so'zning shaxslararo munosabatlardagi ta'sirchanligini oshirish maqsadida hamda ana shunday ijtimoiy faoliyat jarayonida shaxs tizimini takomillashtirishda turli kibernetik modellaridan o'rinli foydalanish zamonaviy psixologiyaning jamiyatdagi o'rnini va rolini oshiradi, maxsus kompyuter dasturlarining keng qo'llanilishi inson miyasi va ruhiy olami sirlarini tez va aniq o'rganishni kafolatlaydi.

6. Texnika fanlari bilan psixologiyaning o'zaro aloqasi va hamkorligi ayniqsa, asr oxiriga kelib yaqqol sezilmoqda. Bir tomondan murakkab texnikani boshqaruvchi inson ongi muammosini echishda, ikkinchi tomondan, psixik hayotning murakkab

qirralarini ochishda maxsus texnik vositalardan foydalanish zarurati bu ikki yo'nalishning erishgan yutuqlarini birlashtirishni nazarda tutadi.

Xulosa

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, ta'kidlangan fan tarmoqlari psixologiya bevosita uzviy aloqada rivojlanadigan fanlarning asosiy qismi xolos. Bugungi kunda har bir fan rivoji uchun inson omilini hisobga olish zarur ekan, psixologiya o'sha barcha fanlar bilan aloqada va hamkorlikda rivojlanadi. Bu tibbiyot, qishloq ho'jaligi, kimyo va oziq-ovqat ishlab chiqarish sanoati, xuquq va madaniyatshunoslik kabi o'nlab fan sohalaridir.

Yuqoridagi fikrlar va psixologiya bevosita aloqador bo'lgan fanlarning xarakteriga bog'liq tarzda bugungi kunda psixologiyadan nisbatan aloxida bo'lib ajralib chiqqan tarmoqlar to'g'risida ham fikr yuritish mumkin deb ayta olamiz.

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